

Studies on some dipolar cycloaddition reactions[†]

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1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition reactions are extensively studied and have a wide range of synthetic applications¹⁻⁶. In the recent past, we have also engaged ourselves⁷ in the dipolar additions of diazomethane, nitrile oxide (1) and nitrones (2, 3). In this lecture it is intended to review our work which covers following aspects.

- Intermolecular additions of diazoalkanes to nitroalkenes and chiral α,β -unsaturated esters and lactones.
- Cycloaddition of cyclic and acyclic nitrones with chiral electrophilic olefins with a particular emphasis on the reaction of allylic oxy-substituted olefins.
- Intramolecular cycloaddition of 3-oxopyrylium ylide – synthesis of enantiomerically pure [5.4.0]bicycloundecane.

In this context several stereochemically well defined chiral dipolarophiles were synthesized (Chart 1) and were condensed with the following 1,3-dipolar species.

Chart 1

The choice of the dipolarophiles was governed by the following considerations :

- * The remoteness of the chiral centre from the site of addition.
- * Nature of the electrophilic olefin.
- * Efficacy of the single and multiple chiral centres and
- * Presence or absence of allylic, allyloxy or alkoxy group.

In this context a series of 3-nitro-2-aryl-2H-1-benzopyrans were prepared and treated with diazomethane

and diazoethane to give various benzopyranopyrazoles⁸ (Scheme 1).

Synthesis of chiral pyrazolines

In view of the reported anti-thrombic activity of pyrazoline derivatives by Fraiser-Reid and coworkers⁹ (Scheme 2), and the reported influence of the nature of allylic oxygen on the level of stereoselection, we have investigated the cycloaddition of diazomethane with chiral unsaturated esters and lactones¹⁰ (Schemes 3–6).

The relative configurations of the cycloadducts 23–50

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Scheme 1

Scheme 2

were assigned on the basis of chemical correlations and NMR analyses. For example, the relative stereochemistry at C₄ and C_{4'} centres of the cycloadducts **23** obtained during the reaction of **10/11** with diazomethane was established through acid catalysed cyclization of the intermediate Δ'-pyrazoline derivative (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

The formation of **25** could be rationalized through the *anti facial* approach of the reactant in the transition state (Fig. 1).

Very similar results were obtained in the cycloaddition of diazomethane to the chiral six-membered unsaturated lactone **15** and esters **12** and its *E* isomer respectively (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5

Esters **12** and **12a** provided the adduct **26**, in which the proton H-7 absorbs at δ 3.56 ppm as a doublet of triplet with *J*_{7,6} 3.20 Hz indicating *trans* relationship between these protons, which in turn indicates an *antifacial* approach

of the reactant in the transition state. Pyranose **15** resulted into a single adduct **27**. All these assignments were corroborated by NOESY experiments. The observed 2D nuclear Overhauser (NOE) interactions are shown in the Fig. 2.

Fig. 2

The 4(*R*)-diastereomer **28a** originated from **14** as a sole product by the addition of diazomethane from the less hindered Re–Re face (Scheme 6, Fig. 3). The proposed structure lend support from the comparable ^{13}C NMR data with that of the diazoadduct of *D*-Galactose derivative¹¹.

Fig. 3

Likewise menthyl acrylate-diazomethane reaction¹⁰ led to the formation of **29** (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7

On the basis of the results obtained, it can be emphasized that the allylic hetero-atom is playing significant role in directing the incoming nucleophile *anti* with respect to its geometry, whereas the bulky group is playing less important role as compared to the hetero-atom. Furthermore, due to immolation of one of the stereogenic centres in the 1-pyrazoline derivatives, the number of stereoisomers obtained will be reduced to half the number of originally anticipated products i.e. one each because of the protopic rearrangement of initially formed 1-pyrazolines to the respective 2-pyrazolines.

Patzel and coworkers¹² have also studied the cycloaddition of diazoalkanes to α,β -unsaturated γ -alkoxy or γ -amino ketones. Similarly, study on menthyl oxy furanone were carried out by Feringa and coworkers¹³.

AM1 Calculations

To evaluate the effect of electrostatic factors in affecting the stereoselectivity of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions, the atomic charges in the transition structure for the cycloaddition reaction for five different 1,3-dipoles to the ethylene were calculated by Annunziata *et al.*^{15a}. According to them if the sense of stereoselectivity is determined by the nature of the substituents at the allylic stereocentre of the alkene, the amount of stereoselectivity is determined by the nature of the 1,3-dipole; in particular, it seems to correlate with the amount of negative charge present on the terminal atom of the dipole moiety^{15b,16} (Fig. 4).

A : nitrene + ethylene TS; B : nitride + ethylene TS;
C : azomethine ylide + ethylene TS; D : diazomethane + ethylene TS.
Mulliken charges on heavy atoms from RHF/3–21 G TSs.

Fig. 4

In order to quantitatively rationalize the observed regioselectivities during the addition of diazomethane, we have also performed FMO analysis on the AM1 calculated frontier orbitals^{13,14,17}. HOMO-LUMO energies (Table 1) were obtained from AM1 optimized geometries. Based on the smaller HOMO-LUMO gap, which involves LUMO of the dipolarophile and HOMO of the dipole, the reaction is predicted to be dipole HOMO controlled in all the cases with electron deficient dipolarophiles, this leads to 3-substitute pyrazoles.

Table 1. AM 1 Calculated FMO energies and atomic contributions

Dipole/Dipolarophile		ΔE (ev)	W	X
$\overset{w}{\text{C}}\text{H}_2=\overset{x}{\text{N}}=\overset{x}{\text{N}}$	HO	-8.822	0.760	-0.627
	LU	1.072	0.561	0.515
	HO	-10.449	0.262	0.343
	LU	-0.216	-0.649	0.488
	HO	-10.574	-0.347	-0.420
	LU	-0.198	-0.611	0.467
	HO	-10.857	0.434	0.523
	LU	-0.467	-0.66	0.533
	HO	-10.576	0.069	0.079
	LU	-0.541	0.645	-0.525
	HO	-10.869	0.225	-0.216
	LU	-0.216	0.467	-0.443

The atom with the larger HOMO-coefficient on the dipole consistently prefers to approach the atom with the larger LUMO-coefficient on the dipolarophile. The observed regiochemistry is correctly predicted by the FMO's derived from AM 1 calculations.

Cycloaddition of nitrones

As in Diels-Alder reaction, the possibility of π -facial selectivity exists in 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction of nitrones involving unsymmetrical substrates^{15,17}. The most interesting examples concern differential reactivities of π -faces induced by subtle perturbation, such as remote substituents. Recently, Houk *et al.*^{16,18c,19} re-examined "the inside alkoxy effect" in the nitrile oxide cycloaddition and showed that electrostatic effect together with the steric effects, may be the origin of the different stereoselectivities observed in cycloaddition reactions of several 1,3-dipoles to chiral alkenes.

Cycloadditions of cyclic achiral nitrones with achiral unsaturated esters and lactones have been reported²⁰; as has been a similar study on acyclic nitrones and chiral unsatur-

ated lactones²¹. However, the behaviour of cyclic achiral/chiral nitrones towards chiral unsaturated esters and lactones; as also that of achiral nitron with chiral unsaturated esters have received very little attention. This prompted us to investigate the regio and stereochemical outcome of the cycloaddition of the chiral unsaturated esters (**10-14**) and sugar lactones such as **15** and **16** and chiral crotonates (**4-9**) with acyclic nitron **1** and five membered cyclic nitrones **2** and **3**.

(A) Cycloaddition of crotonates

2,2-Dimethyl-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-pyrrole-*N*-oxide (**2**) and *N*-(benzylidene) methylamine-*N*-oxide (**1**) were condensed with crotonates (**4-6**) in benzene at 80°. The two adducts obtained from the nitron **2** and the crotonate **4** in the ratio 1 : 8 : 1 were characterized^{22d} as **30a** or **30b** (major) and **30c** or **30d** (minor) (see Scheme 8). The formation of two products (**a** or **b** and **c** or **d**) can be explained by the transition state diagram shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5

Methyl crotonate (**4**) on treatment with **2** under identical conditions gave cycloadduct **31** (**a** or **b**) arising through *endo* transition state (Scheme 8). The diastereoselectivity observed is consistent with that reported in the literature^{23a-c}. While the crotonates (**5** and **6**) produced two diastereomers (Scheme 9) on cycloaddition of the acyclic nitron **1**, only one isomer was obtained from the crotonate **4** (Table 2).

In all the cases (**4-6**), the *trans* configuration between H-3 and H-4 was confirmed by observing the NOESY con-

Scheme 9

Table 2. Cycloaddition of acyclic nitronium 1 with the crotonates

Dipolarophile	Reaction time/h	Solvent (reflux)	Yield (%)	Number of products	Diastereoselectivity ^a
Methyl crotonate	24	CHCl ₃	91	2	1 : 1 <i>endo</i> : <i>exo</i>
4	65	Benzene	82	1	<i>endo</i>
5	60	Benzene	66	2	1 : 1.8
6	48	Benzene	71	2	1 : 1.4 <i>endo</i> : <i>exo</i>

^aDiastereoselectivity expressed in terms of % composition of the adducts.

nectivity between the H-3 and H-5 protons^{22d}. The formation of regiomer *endo* products can be explained with the help of Fig. 6 in which the secondary orbital interactions predominantly favour the formation of *endo* adducts. Formation of 4-carboalkoxy products were also reported by Hamelin and coworkers^{23d} for the cycloaddition of methyl crotonates with acyclic nitrones.

Fig. 6

Cycloaddition of **2** to **7-9** lead to the formation of adducts from 3-*endo*, 3-*exo* and 2-*endo* transition states^{7d}. 3-*endo*-Carboalkoxy products were formed in major amounts in agreement with the FMO theory (Scheme 10). The secondary orbital interactions plays a very important role was clear from the dominance of the *endo*-carboalkoxy products ($\geq 91\%$). Due to large steric bulk of auxiliary alcohols and the *gem* dimethyl substitutions on **2**, electronically unfavourable 2-*endo*-carboalkoxy adducts were formed in substantial quantity (Table 3). The diastereoselectivity (Table 4) via 3-*exo* transition state was negligible, but higher in

case of 2-*endo* and 3-*endo* transition states. The best de was noticed in case of 3-*endo* adducts obtained from **8** (39%).

Scheme 10

Table 3. Percentage composition of the adducts

	(a + b) %	(c + d) %	(e + f) %
7	69	5	26
8	71	9	20
9	79	9	12

Table 4. Diastereomeric ratios due to π -facial selectivity

	c : d	a : b	e : f
7	1.1 : 1	1.6 : 1 ^a	1.4 : 1
8	<i>b</i>	2.3 : 1 ^c	1.3 : 1
9	1.1 : 1	<i>b</i>	1.2 : 1 ^c

^aFrom ¹³C NMR. ^bCould not be assigned. ^cPeaks not resolved to base.

(B) Cycloadducts of esters and lactones

In the case of dipolarophile **10**, addition of the cyclic nitronium **2** gave two *exomeric* 4-substituted products **35** and **36** and an *exomeric* 5-substituted product **37** under chloroform reflux condition. The facial selectivity of the adducts **35** and **36** were proved by cyclization experiments^{21c}. These adducts on acid catalysed cyclization (DOWEX 50 WX8) afforded lactone **38** in 90% yield. A facile lactonization is expected when the alkoxy carbonyl and alcohol functions are *cis*-disposed about the isoxazolidine ring. An identical lactonic cycloadduct should accrue from the lactone **16**, provided the regio and facial selectivity observed in two cases

is same. Indeed, the *exo*-adduct arising from **16** was also identified to be **38** (Scheme 11).

Scheme 11

The formation of **38** supports structure **35** for one of the cycloadducts, which accrues from the Si-Re face of the dienophile. Product **36** having similar structural features except for a difference in spin coupling ($J_{3,3a}$ 4.7 Hz) confirms the opposite facial approach of the dienophile in the Re-Si transition state (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7

However, acyclic nitron **1** sluggishly reacted with **10** to produce four isomeric products **39a-d** (Scheme 12).

Scheme 12

The reaction between nitron **1** and butenolide **16** yielded two isomers **40a** and **40b**. The two isomers differ from each other only by the *endo/exo* mode of addition of the dipole in the transition state (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8

E-isomer **11**, on the other hand, on treatment with **2** resulted into 2-*endo* adducts **41** and **42** in equal ratio. In this case, face selectivity could not be ascertained due to the liberation of C5-C4' single bond (Scheme 13).

Scheme 13

Of the possible eight isomers only diastereomer **43** was formed on interacting pyranone **15** with **2**. An incisive spectroscopic study (Fig. 9) has established an *exo*-approach of the reactant from the Si-Re face in the transition state (Chart 2). Likewise *exo*-adduct **44** was obtained from the interaction of **15** and **1** (Scheme 14).

Compound **44** can arise either from the *Z*-nitron reacting with the dipolarophile by an *exo* attack or *E*-nitron by an *endo* attack. Since nitron **1** is known to exist predominantly in *Z*-form, therefore adduct **44** arises from the *exo* attack of the dipole (Chart 2).

The *trans* dipolarophile **14** reacted with the cyclic nitron

Scheme 14

30 NOE

Fig. 9

Chart 2

2 on refluxing in benzene to give two *endo*-adducts **45** and **46**. The cycloadducts derived from **1** and **14** were character-

ized as **47** and **48** having *exo*-configuration (Scheme 15).

Scheme 15

Since the cycloadducts **45** and **46** are not the regiomers, they should differ only by the facial approach of the dipole in the transition state (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10

Both cyclic and acyclic nitrones **1** and **2** on cycloaddition with symmetrically disubstituted *trans*-dipolarophile **13** elaborated single adducts **49** and **50** respectively (Scheme 16).

Scheme 16

In almost all the cases, cyclic nitron reacted much faster than the acyclic nitron. The observed product ratios, reaction time and temperature for the same cycloaddition reactions are summarized in Tables 5 and 6 respectively.

Table 5. Cycloaddition of a cyclic nitron 2 with esters and lactones

Dipolarophile	Reaction time/h	Solvent (reflux)	Yield (%)	Number of products	Relative ratios
10	65	CHCl ₃	76	3	4 : 1 : 2 (14 : 17 : 13)
11	200	Toluene	55	2	1 : 1 (22 : 21)
14	100	Benzene	85	2	1 : 1.5
13	48	CHCl ₃	76	1	–
16	60	CHCl ₃	66	1	–
15	72	CHCl ₃	78	1	–

Table 6. Cycloaddition of a cyclic nitron 2 with esters and lactones

Dipolarophile	Reaction time/h	Solvent (reflux)	Yield (%)	Number of products	Relative ratios
10	120	Toluene	60	4	1 : 1 : 1.5 : 2 (32a : b : c : d)
11	120	Toluene	NR	–	–
14	120	Toluene	55 ^a	2	1.6 : 1
13	48	Benzene	70	1	–
16	48	CHCl ₃	66	2	1.2 : 1
15	30	Benzene	69 ^a	1 ^b	–

^aStarting material recovered from the column. ^bMore than one product observed on TLC and could not be isolated.

The approaches used to control the relative and absolute stereochemistry depends on the use of homochiral nitrones²⁴. Prompted by this observation, we undertook the study of the behavior of a stereogenic nitron towards an optically pure dipolarophile^{22b}.

(±)-4,5,5-Trimethyl-Δ1-pyrroline-1-oxide (3) reacted readily with 14 in anhydrous benzene to give a product from which a mixture comprising of two diastereomeric isoxazolidines A and B in the ratio 60 : 40 could be isolated (Scheme 17).

Scheme 17

The structure and configurations of both of the diastereomers were determined through the use of the (¹H-¹H) COSY, (¹³C-¹H) HETCOR and NOEDS Experiments. The NOEDS data for both the adducts are given in the Table 7.

The diastereomers A and B differed in configuration at C-5 and were identified as (2α,3β,3αα,5β)- and (2α,3β,3αα,5α)-ethyl hexahydro-2-(1,2,3,4-tetraacetoxy butyl)-5,6,6-trimethyl pyrrolo-[1,2-*b*]-isoxazole-3-carboxylate respectively.

The regioselectivity of nitron cycloaddition reactions are inconsistent with FMO energies^{22e} and could be explained on the basis of charge distribution through AMI calculations^{22e}.

Table 7. NOEDS data for compounds A and B

A

B

Compound A:	Enhancement observed	Proton irradiated			
		H ₃	15-CH ₃	16-CH ₃	17-CH ₃
H-2	4	–	–	2.6	
H-3a	10.7	–	9.7	–	
H-5	–	12.2	–	12.9	
H-8	13.6	–	–	–	
H-9	–	–	–	1.8	
H-16	–	1.1	–	1.8	
H-17	–	–	3	–	

Compound B:	Enhancement observed	Proton irradiated			
		H-2 ^a	H-3 ^a	15-CH ₃	17-CH ₃ ^b
H-2	–	2.9	1.5	8.4	
H-3	2.8	–	–	–	
H-3a	–	11.4 ^c	–	–	
H-5	–	–	8.8	–	
H-8	3.9 ^c	12.9 ^c	–	–	
H-9	3.3 ^c	–	–	–	
H-15	–	–	–	0.7	
H-17	0.6	–	1.2	–	

^aPartial saturation of corresponding signal of compound A. ^bPartial saturation of 16-CH₃. ^cOverlap of tickling component of A.

Asymmetric synthesis of oxa bridged bicyclo[5.4.0]undecanes

3-Oxidopyrylium salts constitute yet another interesting class of dipolar system^{25–27}. Cycloaddition reactions of six membered heteroaromatic betains with positive charge on

oxygen²⁸ offer fascinating chemistry. Oxidopyrylium-alkene [5 + 2]cycloaddition constitutes an excellent way for the synthesis of bicyclo[3.2.1]octane framework from simple precursors^{29,30}. Conceptually, a [5 + 2]cycloaddition reaction involves the reaction of a five-carbon species (4π) with a two atom species (2π). The reactive species such as **51**, a 3 oxo pyrylium ylide, behaves as a five carbon partner and readily cycloadds to a two-carbon unit (a dipolarophile) to give the adducts of the type **52** and or **53** (Scheme 18).

Scheme 18

Initially Hendrickson²⁶ studied the reaction with electron-deficient dipolarophiles; but subsequently Sammes^{29a} found that the reaction is equally applicable to electron-rich and strained olefinic dipolarophiles. The rapid generation of molecular complexity in relatively easy manner, made this approach highly useful in the synthesis of seven membered ring containing complex natural products^{30,31}. However, compared to other cycloaddition strategies one of the most important aspects which has received relatively less attention is the asymmetric version of the cycloaddition.

Recently, Mascernas and coworkers³² have reported a chiral auxiliary approach for the synthesis of enantiopure oxabridge bicyclo[5.3.0]decane. The strategy involved preparation of TMS ether of 2-furylcarbinol **54**, transformation of the furan derivative into the pyranone **55** and base catalysed intramolecular cycloaddition of the *in situ* generated 3-oxidopyrylium species. The cycloadduct **56** on desulfination yielded oxa-bridged (+)-**57** (Scheme 19).

Scheme 19

We also directed our investigation towards the asymmetric synthesis of oxa-bridged bicyclo[5.4.0]undecanes employing readily available D-ribose³⁴. Our synthesis began with the preparation of the aldehyde **58** from D-ribose³³ (Scheme 20).

Scheme 20

The furyl carbinols **59** derived from **58** was oxidatively rearranged to the pyranone **60** using Vo (acac) 2/*t*-BuOOH. Intramolecular cycloaddition of the acetoxy pyranone **61** in the presence of base afforded adducts **62** and **63** as inseparable mixture of diastereomers (93 : 7) (Scheme 21).

Scheme 21

The observed preference for the *trans*-fused ring system and diastereoselectivity can be explained by involving the rationale given by Wander^{31b,c} and Williams^{31e,f} respectively. According to Wander, the stereochemical outcome of the intramolecular [5 + 2]cycloaddition is controlled by the tether and the orientation of the methyl group (Scheme 22).

Scheme 22

Williams and coworkers^{312,f} proposed adoption of two chair like arrangements (**A** and **B**) during the cycloaddition of the pyranose **64**.

According to these authors, an equatorial disposition of the oxido substituent in **A** leads to the *trans*-fused product **65**. However, chair like conformer **B**, displays an unfavourable non-bonded interaction between the vinylic methyl and the developing axial methoxy (at C₁), as well as a serious interaction of the tether (C₄) allylic methylene and the oxido-function (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11

In order to explore the role of stereochemistry in analogous [5 + 2]cycloadditions, the pseudo symmetry of ribose was exploited. It was envisioned that introduction of the furyl unit in the lactol **67** (Scheme 23) would provide an intermediate, which may allow the reversal of the sense of the asymmetric induction compared to our afore mentioned intramolecular cycloaddition. Accordingly, 2,3-*O*-isopropylidene-D-ribose (**66**) was transformed to the lactol **67**. Following the methodology developed in our laboratory lactol **67** was converted to the acetylpyranone **68**, which upon treatment with triethylamine in methylcyanide underwent a highly stereoselective cycloaddition to yield the adduct **69**, as a sole product.

Scheme 23

The stereostructure of **69** was ascertained by X-ray crystallography (Fig. 12). It is noteworthy that the adducts **62** and **69**, as expected, are having enantiomeric relationship. We are presently investigating the generality of the methodology developed in our laboratory.

Fig. 12

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